

VARIOUS SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL ANALYSIS IN THE STUDY OF CONFIDENCE IN ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation: in the article, increasing the level of trust in adolescent children is mainly focused on studying their confidence, knowledge levels, socio-psychological characteristics, while studying the psychological states, characteristics, and levels of trust in boys and girls is mainly focused on studying their knowledge level and relationships with others. In increasing the sense of confidence, along with the level of knowledge of adolescents, their intellect plays an important role. It's worth noting that relatives and teachers play a major role in increasing confidence. It has been shown that the level of confidence in adolescents is initially weak, and gradually develops.

Keywords: adolescent, belief, emotion, knowledge, intellect, consequence, attention, imagination, perception, thinking, consistency of thoughts, parents, memory, family well-being.

Kirish.

Mamlakatimiz barcha sohalarda ilg'or va taraqqiy etib borayotgani hech birimizga sir emas, zero O'zbekiston mustaqillikga erishgach har jabhada salmoqli ishlarni amalga oshirib ,tub islohotlarni olib borgan, hususan ta'lim tizimida ham o'zgarishlar bo'lganligi va bu o'zgarishlarning barcha barchasi yosh avlod va uning kelajagiga qaratilganligi bejiz emas. Prezidentimiz SH.M.Mirziyoyev o'zining "Yangi O'zbekiston Strategiyasi" asarida ta'kidlaganidek. "Maktab – faqatgina ta'lim beradigan maskan emas, barchamiz uchun yuksak ma'naviyat beshigiga farzandlarimizni bolalikdan boshlab kasbga o'rgatuvchi dargohga aylanishi zarur".

Training specialists with consistent knowledge and practical skills who can

successfully solve new modern problems is one of the urgent problems of today. Since the development and prosperity of our republic depends on young people, it is necessary to educate them as fully developed people. Properly organizing the joint activities of a teacher and a teenager is one of the main factors in the professional training of future specialists. In our country, during the discussion of the draft of the new “Law on Education”, it is aimed to create professionals in their profession, highly intelligent, with strong intellectual potential, embodying a perfect worldview and rich spirituality, and to achieve their competitiveness in the world community. Therefore, educating the personality of a teenager and a teenager, the future generation as a mature person with a healthy and independent mind, has become one of the main tasks set today. One of the problems that psychologists face today is to study interpersonal relationships and personality traits in groups of students as fully and perfectly as possible.

Identifying the socio-psychological characteristics of trust in people in adolescents.

Adolescence is one of the most dynamic stages in the psychological development of a person. In this process, the category of trust is considered a central component of interpersonal relationships in psychology. According to Erikson's theory of psychosocial development, the initial foundations of trust are formed in the early stages of childhood, but in adolescence it is reinforced, supplemented in terms of content, and improved in connection with social status. Erikson describes adolescence as a “period of identification and role choice” and emphasizes that trust at this stage is one of the pillars of psychosocial stability.

According to representatives of cognitive psychology, in particular, J. Piaget, as the processes of abstract thinking, reflection, and self-awareness deepen in adolescence, a person's assessment of trust also becomes more complex. Adolescents begin to evaluate the behavior of others not only by their appearance,

but also based on motivational and moral criteria. This process forms the basis for the formation of the cognitive component of trust.

Representatives of humanistic psychology (Maslow, Rogers) interpret trust as a quality that is inextricably linked to a person's psychological well-being, self-esteem, and emotional security. Rogers' principles of "accepting, unconditional respect" are seen as the main psychotherapeutic mechanism in the development of trust. In adolescence, these principles are manifested in communication with peers, through the quality of communication in the family, and through the principles of justice in the pedagogical process.

The family is the primary socializer of the adolescent, and the main foundation of trust is formed precisely through family relationships. Studies show that in families where there is mutual respect, affection, emotional closeness, justice and consistent control, adolescents have a high level of trust. On the contrary, in a conflictive, indifferent, excessively authoritarian environment, the level of distrust increases.

According to the point of view of attachment theory (Bowlby, Ainsworth), a secure attachment model provides a teenager with internal stability, self-confidence, positive attitude towards others and social adaptation. Insecure attachment increases distrust, anxiety, aggressive reactions and emotional sensitivity.

In the pedagogical process, a teacher's fair, consistent, supportive or, conversely, derogatory and indifferent attitude has a significant impact on the formation of trust in adolescents. Constructive communication, an individual approach, and recognition of the student's value in the educational process increase the level of trust.

According to social learning theory (Bandura), adolescents create social models by observing the behavior of those around them. A positive example from

teachers and peers strengthens trust; aggression, discrimination, and indifference increase distrust. Adolescence is a period when peer relationships have the strongest influence. Sociometric studies show that adolescents with high social status and developed communication skills have a strong sense of trust. Adolescents who are excluded from society, rejected, or bullied often experience insecurity, anxiety, and a sense of worthlessness.

As Erikson noted, adolescence is a period of formation of personal identity. Adolescents with high self-esteem tend to trust others, because they perceive social assessments adequately. Low self-esteem is one of the strongest predictors of distrust. Theoretical understanding and study of the phenomenon of trust has a long history, it is covered in the philosophical works of Aristotle, Plato, Spinoza, T. Hobbes, N. Machiavelli, J. Locke, J.J. Rousseau, D. Hume, I. Kant, G. Hegel and other famous philosophers. In their works, trust is presented as a moral category that reflects moral standards and relationships between people. Almost all authors studying the category of trust emphasize that trust is a qualitatively unique state of mind. This includes moral feelings and beliefs, which are the causes or incentives of a person's behavior. In this regard, trust appears as a means of regulating moral relations, and here philosophers consider its main function to be precisely this. However, the concept of "trust" is also a psychological phenomenon, since it serves as the basis for interpersonal relationships, the interaction of a person with the world and himself. Different dictionaries give different definitions of trust, but they also have a common feature in understanding trust - belief in someone's truthfulness, belief in the honesty and nobility of a person.

METHODOLOGY OF LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

The concept of "trust" has been put forward as a simple reflection of the practice of everyday relationships between people. Eastern scholars Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Russian scholars E. Erikson, S.L. Rubinstein, E. Fromm,

S. Kierkegaard, R.V. Emerson, in their studies, directly examined how the concept of trust arises, stating that trust first appears in the family, in the circle of friends, and during school years, that is, trust arises less in adolescents, because at that age they need more affection and kind words (1.79 b)

Analysis shows that the emergence of the concept of trust is mainly due to socio-psychological factors, labor processes, overcoming fear, distrust, etc. Sh.R.Baratov, N.G.Kamilova, G.K.Tulyaganova and others conducted scientific research.

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, we can say that if we compare the feeling of confidence in girls and boys based on the table, we can see that girls have higher levels of confidence when comparing the two, the main reason for this is that they are curious, have their own opinions, and express their thoughts freely. If we look at the urban-rural intersection, we can see that teenagers in urban areas have higher levels of confidence.

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